

SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL ADAPTATION AND REHABILITATION OF AIDS PATIENTS IN SOCIETY

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Abstract. The article provides an overview of modern Uzbek and foreign publications on the topic of coping with the disease in people living with HIV. Strategies for coping with HIV/AIDS, psychological factors of effective coping with the disease and existing experience in preventive interventions are considered.

Keywords: HIV/AIDS, coping strategies, stress, people living with HIV/AIDS, coping with stress, prevention.

INTRODUCTION

Despite ongoing efforts to prevent and contain the epidemic, HIV incidence and AIDS mortality rates are among the highest in the world. In this regard, one of the most pressing scientific tasks is the study of psychosocial mechanisms and factors that influence the coping of people living with HIV (PLHIV) with the disease.

Coping with HIV infection has its own specifics compared to coping with other diseases. This disease 1) is incurable and without proper treatment can be fatal, 2) in Uzbek society for a long time it was widespread mainly among marginalized social groups (drug users, people involved in prostitution, men practicing homosexual behavior), 3) is associated with a negative reaction from society, the phenomena of stigmatization and discrimination.

Coping with HIV infection also has specific indicators for its measurement. In addition to indicators of physical and psychological well-being and quality of life, researchers use as indicators of successful coping the high adherence of patients to antiretroviral therapy and the general course of treatment, as well as measures to reduce the risk of infection of others taken by PLHIV (using a condom, disclosing HIV status, refusal to transfer your own used injection equipment to other people).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Traditionally, researchers assess the process of coping with HIV infection using the concept of coping strategies. It should be noted, however, that at the moment there is no common understanding of this concept both in Uzbekistan [2] and abroad. In order to be convinced of this, it is enough just to turn to a critical review of methods for measuring coping behavior by Ralph and Christine

Schwarzer [3, p. 107–132] or to the work of E.A. Skinner et al. [4], in which they identified four hundred coping strategies.

There are various techniques for measuring the severity of various coping strategies. When studying HIV-positive people in Uzbekistan, methods such as the “Coping Test” of Lazarus and Folkman are usually used [1], the method for determining individual coping strategies by E. Heim [2] and others, non-specific for this target group. A systematic review of English-language publications [3] showed the active use in Western literature of at least ten different methods for determining coping strategies, including in the field of coping with various diseases. The most commonly used is the “COPE” questionnaire, which was only recently adapted in Uzbekistan [1]. There are also a number of specialized techniques for assessing strategies for coping with stress specific to PLHIV, which, however, have not yet found widespread use in Uzbekistan.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Overall, studies to date have shown that passive coping strategies, such as denial, are associated with greater progression of HIV infection [3]. Data from meta-analytic studies suggest that strategies such as Direct Action and Positive Reappraisal are more effective in terms of psychological and physical well-being for HIV-positive people. Forms of coping behavior such as Use of Alcohol or Drugs to Cope and Behavioral Disengagement are consistently associated with negative psychological and medical outcomes [4]. An analysis by J. Friedland et al. [5] showed a close positive relationship between problem- and perception-oriented strategies and the quality of life of PLHIV. Emotionally oriented coping, on the contrary, was negatively associated with quality of life.

Also, longitudinal empirical studies have confirmed the connection between positive religious strategies, such as seeking spiritual support, and improving the psychophysiological state of a patient with HIV infection. Negative religious strategies, for example, anger at God, on the contrary, do not lead to an improvement in these indicators.

In science, significant attention is paid to the study of coping strategies specific to PLHIV. In the dissertation research of I.V. Tukhtarova showed a higher prevalence among PLHIV of such ineffective strategies as distancing, escape-avoidance and confrontational coping, and a less frequent use of strategies for planning a solution to the problem, positive reappraisal, seeking social support, self-control and taking responsibility. It should be noted, however, that 72% of respondents from the experimental group also had a diagnosis of heroin addiction, which makes it difficult to interpret the results.

Factors of coping with HIV infection

Psychosocial factors are among the most powerful predictors of successful coping with the disease. They influence both directly and through behavior change, in the area of psychoactive substance use, treatment adherence and lifestyle, which are mediator factors in this case.

Numerous studies demonstrate a direct connection between the presence of depression in patients and poor outcomes of HIV treatment [2]. Most of these studies, however, were cross-sectional in design, which does not allow for causal relationships to be determined. Data from a relatively small number of longitudinal studies tend to confirm the hypothesis that depression is a factor in the deterioration of physical condition in PLHIV, and not vice versa [3]. Depression is the most common mental disorder among HIV-infected patients. It is possible that lower treatment adherence among women may be associated with a higher incidence of depressive symptoms. Treating depression and receiving mental health care has been noted to help improve adherence.

A series of longitudinal studies in several countries around the world have shown an extremely high prevalence of childhood sexual abuse and other traumatic events. Experience of sexual violence and other psychological trauma were strong predictors of low adherence to antiretroviral therapy, unprotected sex, worse physical health and higher mortality rates. In addition, HIV-infected people who experienced stressful life events (such as acute financial problems or the death of a loved one) had lower rates of treatment adherence and were more likely to practice unsafe sex.

Such current psychosocial characteristics of adaptation as depression and stress are associated with patients' weak faith in the effectiveness of antiretroviral therapy and their own ability to overcome the disease. The positive relationship between self-efficacy, that is, the feeling of control over the successful outcome of one's actions, belief in one's ability to act so that these actions lead to the desired result, and coping with HIV infection has been consistently confirmed in a number of empirical studies [2].

A direct and indirect positive effect of the desire for spiritual growth (spiritual striving) on depressive symptoms was also revealed, which was partially mediated by the coping strategy of acceptance [3].

Longitudinal studies have shown that characteristics of the wider social environment and reference group have a significant influence on coping. Thus, the perceived stigmatization of PLHIV, that is, this group's perception of the

degree of negative attitude toward it from society, has a strong negative impact on the quality of life [3].

Conversely, social support has a powerful positive effect on coping with HIV infection by increasing self-efficacy and reducing stress and depression [4]. A number of studies have shown that a lack of social support (both emotional and instrumental) was associated with faster disease progression and the development of AIDS. At the same time, a level of social support that is inadequate to needs can have both negative psychological and negative physiological consequences. In general, it has been noted that higher levels of social support are associated with better functioning of the immune system. Social indicators directly related to social support such as absence of a spouse and homelessness also have a strong correlation with lower rates of adherence to antiretroviral therapy.

Patients whose relatives and friends know about their HIV status have higher rates of life satisfaction. Researchers also tend to interpret this relationship in terms of increased social support and social capital and propose preventive interventions aimed at increasing social capital in people living with HIV. Also, disclosing one's HIV status can be considered as a specific coping strategy. One qualitative study showed that disclosure of HIV status increased practical and emotional social support, acceptance of the condition by the respondent himself, and also helped to share responsibility for the risk of HIV transmission through sexual contacts. It should be noted that the process of disclosing HIV status can also simultaneously be a powerful stressor [4].

Opportunities for improving coping characteristics among PLHIV

Most published results of interventions aimed at improving coping characteristics in PLHIV are based on the cognitive-behavioral paradigm. They are mainly aimed at improving mental health indicators, reducing symptoms of stress, anxiety and depression. A systematic review of published results of preventive interventions found that 60% of cases showed significant positive changes in target indicators, but there was also a large proportion of interventions that did not show effectiveness and had mixed results - for example, only short-term improvements in mental health indicators, which were subsequently leveled out [4].

CONCLUSION

It should be noted that, despite the significant experience of successful preventive interventions, assessing their effectiveness still has many methodological limitations, including due to the lack of random selection of

project participants and/or the lack of assessment of the sustainability of the results obtained in the long term. In addition, these interventions typically consist of multiple sessions of varying formats and have many different components, making it difficult to assess which intervention components are key or most effective [5]. Due to the ongoing HIV epidemic in Uzbekistan, there is a high need for the development and sociocultural adaptation of interventions that are effective in improving the coping characteristics of PLHIV.

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